

Understanding Personal Finance for Students & Lifelong Success

By

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ORCID ID: 0009-0002-0895-7010

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11479635

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2024

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Date:

5/17/2024

5/24/2024

About the Author

Gabriel Ramirez is a first-generation business student at California State University, Fullerton, where he specializes in investments and corporate finance. Growing up in a low-income environment, Gabriel was determined to become financially literate, so he immersed himself into the world of finance to ensure he would have the knowledge to build wealth. He has been an active member in the university's Student Managed Investment Fund & Finance Association, where he collaborated with his peers about financial markets and utilized his skills in financial analysis to build well-balanced portfolios. Gabriel gained experience through a commercial real estate internship where he learned about equity and debt financing, deal sourcing, and utilizing financial modeling. He intends to pursue a career in asset management and to obtain his CFA. Beyond his professional goals, Gabriel aspires to help fellow college students become financially literate and to equip them with the skills for lifelong success.

Introduction

Student financial literacy and success is currently at an inadequate level which can not only adversely affect their personal finances, but also their mental health & lifelong success. Financial literacy matters because it has a direct correlation between financial stability and mental health problems like depression and anxiety (Camberato 2022). Mental health is linked to how well students perform their tasks and it is essential that students do not stress about their finances as they are already overwhelmed with school. It is important to restate it as that is the main issue that is plaguing students and one, I am trying to solve with this project. Many students do not have any idea what a Roth IRA account even is or what the difference between subsidized and unsubsidized loan are. These are just a few, but simple things students should know because it directly applies to them and their future. According to *Journal of Financial Education*, “All indications to date seem to suggest that most students’ financial literacy level is low” (Nonis 27). This project is dedicated to helping students become financially literate by going through a deep analysis on the four financial pillars which are: savings, investing, credit, assets & liabilities. These pillars represent the foundation of a successful, educated generation. The project includes valuable insight on the financial pillars from the director of the university’s “Certified Financial Planner” program. A comprehensive survey of college students conducted to see if there is a lack of financial literacy within the student population. To inform this project, extensive research has been carried out on financial instruments and how students can utilize them to optimize their finances. The university offers a finance course available to all students that thoroughly covers personal finance called Finance 310 “Personal Financial Management.” Investing in financial literacy is investing in the future leaders and well-being of our generation, allowing us to make better life decisions.

Savings

Savings is probably the simplest aspect of personal finance to understand. There is not much complexity around savings, and it is a good fundamental to start with. In my personal information gathered by fellow California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) students, 53% of students were very well informed and 47% were sort of informed of savings/budgeting. That means that in that small research over 90% of candidates were at least aware of savings. Furthermore, there are many aspects of savings that students are not aware of such as; high-yield savings account, certificate of deposits, and emergency funds. High yield saving accounts allow students to earn a higher interest rate on their money than they are currently making in traditional savings accounts. According to *Bankrate*, “The national average yield for savings accounts is 0.58% APY as of May 2024” (Goldberg). On the contrary, typical high yield savings accounts offer 4.00% - 5.00% APY which is more than five times that of a traditional savings account. This allows for not only a greater return on their savings, but it increases the future value of their money. There are various institutions that offer competitive rates such as; Barclay’s, So-Fi, Ally Financial, Discover and Marcus by Goldman Sachs.

Account	Annual Percentage Yield	Minimum Deposit Required	Monthly Maintenance Fee
Barclay’s	4.35%	\$0	\$0
So-Fi	4.60%	\$0	\$0
Ally Financial	4.20%	\$0	\$0
Discover	4.25%	\$0	\$0
Marcus	4.40%	\$0	\$0

Another benefit of heigh-yield savings accounts besides their high Annual Percentage Rate is that they are FDIC insured up to \$250,000. This means that there is little to no risk in having money in a high yield savings account. The main drawback of these accounts is that most of them are online banks and do not have physical brick-and-mortar locations. They also have policies on how often you can withdraw money from the account, making it inconvenient to access money if you need it quickly. The rates in high-yield savings are not fixed, which means

they can fluctuate up or down. Moreover, certificates of deposit are another great alternative to traditional savings accounts. They are similar to high-yield savings accounts in which they provide high interest rates, increasing the future value of the money, but certificates of deposit are much shorter term and offer fixed rates. Certificates of deposit usually offer higher interest rates than high-yield savings account, but it truly depends on the maturity of the certificate. A short-term certificate of deposit (ex. 6 months) is likely to have a fixed yield of around 5.00%, but a longer the maturity certificate will most likely have a lower yield. One of the biggest downsides of certificate of deposits is that you must wait until the CD matures to withdraw the money or else there will be penalized for early withdrawal. In addition, most traditional certificates of deposit have a minimum deposit required in order to utilize the certificate. The formula for calculating future value is $FV = PV(1 + r)^n$, where PV = present value, r= annual interest rate and n= number of periods interest is held. This formula can be utilized for both high yield savings accounts and certificates of deposit. For example, let's assume you put \$1000 in a certificate of deposit that offers 5.00% APY and has a maturity of 6 months. Then, $FV = 1000(1 + .05)^{\frac{6}{12}}$ is equal to \$1024.35 which is \$24.35 of risk-free money and made without moving a finger. Moreover, an emergency fund is a fund utilized to save money in case of any unpredictable financial blows. The recommended amount of money to have set aside in an emergency fund is about three to six months of living expenses. According to HanNa (CFP Director), "The recommended amount of money to have in an emergency fund is about three to six months of living expenses. The main point of an emergency fund is to have money set aside for any unexpected adverse financial situations." In addition, it is best if the money is saved in highly liquid accounts that earn interest such as high-yield savings and short-term certificates of deposit. It is important to have money set aside for those rainy days. Finally, savings allow for an orchestrated distribution of income into different segments and investment plans. According to

Taylor & Francis Group, “the additional planned savings flow is equal to the additional investment flow” (Davidson 109). The money that is saved up in the savings account can be utilized in future investments to bring in cashflow rather than sitting in a bank and earning a fixed rate. Essentially utilizing the money to invest into starting new businesses, buying real estate, investing in the stock market, and fixed income investments.

Investing

One of the important aspects of personal finance is investing. Investing allows money to keep on growing and hold its value against inflation. There are various ways to invest in order to diversify your portfolio and mitigate risks. The four most common ways to invest money are stocks, bonds, real estate, and commodities. Nonetheless, there are better ways to invest that are of lower risk, less upfront cost and offer good yields. These are investments such as; treasury bonds, mutual funds, index funds and common stocks with dividends. According to *Forbes*, “Examples of low-risk investing include buying treasury securities, corporate bonds, money market mutual funds, fixed annuities, preferred stocks, common stocks that pay dividends and index funds”(Treece 2022). For students, I recommend that they open a brokerage account and begin to invest on their own. Usually when you invest with the help of a financial advisor there are big commission fees and payments. My brokage recommendations for students are Webull, Robinhood, Charles Schwab, Fidelity, and So-Fi. These accounts offer great services and little to no minimum payments. There are no commission fees if you have a self-direct account and no account minimum balance. Moreover, in simple terms, investing in bonds is buying debt. When buying treasury bonds, it is almost guaranteed that you will not lose money, but the yield on the bond is not as high as riskier bonds such as a corporate bonds. Treasury bonds are debt securities issued by the United States government to investors. They have various maturities but are typically longer term ranging from 10-year to 30-year maturities. According to *American*

Economic Review, “US government bonds are widely considered to be the world’s safe store of value. US government bonds are a large fraction of safe asset portfolios, such as the portfolios of many central banks”(He, Zhiguo). If you are a risk averse investor, then treasury bills are a fantastic way to not only invest but diversify your portfolio to reduce risk. Furthermore, investing in mutual funds allows for your money to be diversified into even more investments that can bring in a higher return on investment (ROI). Mutual funds are funds that let you combine your money with other investors to “mutually” buy bonds, stocks, or any investments. The money in the fund is then run by a professional money manager who decides what to buy and when to sell them. It is a great way to have your money managed, especially by experienced professionals. Mutual Fund’s main purpose is that they allow for diversification, offer low costs, are very convenient and allow for professional management. According to *USA Today*, “The five best mutual funds for 2024 are Fidelity 500 Index Fund (FXAIX), Fidelity Total Market Index Funds (FSKAX), Schwab S&P 500 Index Fund (SWPPX), Schwab Total Stock Market Index Fund (SWTSX), and Vanguard 500 Index Fund Admiral Shares (VFIAX)”(Powell). Mutual funds are very similar to index funds, but index funds allow for a low-risk investment in which it invests money into major S&P 500 companies and are more passively managed by financial

professionals.

The graph above shows the returns of the S&P 500 Index from 2003 to 2023, showing that it increases in value, builds wealth and hedges against inflation. Finally, students can open brokerage accounts and invest in individual stocks. When buying a company stock, you are essentially being a part owner of the company on a micro level, called a share. The main goal in buying company stock is the hope that the value of the company goes up. Individual stocks historically offer the highest returns compared to cash and bonds but also have the highest risk. Take NVIDIA for example, if you had invested in NVIDIA exactly one year ago, you would have made a 206% return on your investment which is higher than any of the previous options

can offer.

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Key events

Although returns like this are not common at all, it does show that having the right investment at the right time it can definitely pay off. On the other hand, it is possible that an investment in individual stocks can also drop significantly, and you must be aware of the risks that you are taking. In addition, investing in common stock with dividends is a fantastic way to make passive income. For example, Chevron (CVX) pays its stockholders \$1.42 per share in dividends, meaning that if you own 100 shares that will be \$142 of passive income per quarter. This is a great way to build a passive income portfolio and ensure that you earn dividends whether the stock goes up or down. Overall, there are many ways to invest out there, whether it be stocks, precious metals or even artwork, it is better to invest than have money just under a mattress. As young students with a longer time horizon, it is best to invest in equity rather than fixed income due to it offering a higher return over time. According to *Investopedia*, "For example, one hundred dollars invested in the Standard & Poor's 500 Index (S&P 500) in 1928 would have been

worth more than \$700,000 by 2021. In comparison, the same \$100 invested in 10-year Treasuries for the same time period would have been worth only a little more than \$8,500”(Investopedia Team). It is recommended to have an 80/20 portfolio split with the majority being in equity. Lastly, I want to cover the importance of opening a retirement account, whether traditional or Roth IRA. An IRA stands for Individual Retirement Account and its main purpose is to save and invest for retirement. As previously mentioned, if you do not invest and let your money grow, inflation will slowly creep up and the money will start to lose value. This means that holding on to cash as a form of retirement is not an optimal way to save for retirement. A Roth IRA is an individual retirement account to which you contribute after-tax dollars and enables you to put aside up to \$7,000 to save and invest for retirement. The true power is that once you retire all the money you accumulated can be withdrawn tax free. Furthermore, a traditional IRA is a retirement account in which it is utilized more specifically for tax deferring reasons. This is more optimal for individuals who have a huge income and want tax deductible benefits.

IRA Brokers	Fees	Account Minimum
Charles Schwab	\$0	\$0
Fidelity	\$0	\$0
Vanguard	0.15% (per year)	\$3000
JP Morgan	\$0	\$0

According to NerdWallet.com

Overall, this is an amazing way for students to start saving for retirement as starting early means more time for your money to grow and it is completely up to you to choose which one makes the most sense for your situation and future goals.

Credit Management

Credit is important to college students who are now starting their adult life, however, they are not often taught the proper way to use and build credit. Many students suffer from poor credit management and misuse the money leading them to debt. There are various things that students

should know about credit, but the most important are student credit cards, understanding annual percentage rate (APR) and how to establish and increase their credit. Firstly, for those students who do not have any credit history let alone a credit card, a great way to start is by applying for a student credit card. A student credit card gives students the opportunity to build positive credit history by utilizing the credit card and making payments on time. Some student credit cards even offer rewards to students such as cash back and travel points. This is a fantastic way to incentivize students to use credit, while also reaping the rewards of cash back and establishing credit. Some popular issuers of student credit cards are Discover, Capital One, Bank of America and Citibank. Most student credit card issuers also do not charge an annual fee which is great for students. The downside to student credit cards is that they usually offer low credit limits and high interest rates compared to traditional credit cards. It is important to use the card responsibly and pay your bills on time to avoid going into debt. This ties in with my second topic which is understanding annual percentage rate (APR). The annual percentage rate of a credit card refers to the yearly interest rate you will be charged on your credit card balance. Credit card issuers are known to charge high interest rates varying from 15.00% to even 29.99% APR. If you make your payments on time and pay in full, you do not have to worry about the APR. According to *Consumer Financial Protection Bureau*, “On most cards, you can avoid paying interest on purchases if you pay your balance in full each month by the due date”. Nonetheless, it is the high interest rate that keeps people stuck in credit card debt and makes it hard to pay off. It is important to not do the minimum payments as the debt balance will only continue to increase. Finally, I will cover ways to not only establish credit, but to increase your credit score. Credit scores range from 300 to 850, meaning that those are the absolute maximum and minimum.

Credit Score Range	Meaning
800 to 850	Excellent: Considerably the best credit score possible. May qualify for favorable rates.

740 to 799	Very Good: Strong credit score shows that you are responsible.
670 to 739	Good: Shows that you are trustworthy but will not receive ideal interest rates.
580 to 669	Fair: Average credit score will still be able to qualify for some loans.
300 to 579	Poor: Difficulty applying for loans and will receive high interest rates.

The most used model in the United States is the FICO score which is utilized to generate a credit score. The top two things that affect over 60% of your credit score are paying your bills on time and reducing the amount of debt you owe. According to *MyFICO.com*, “Making payments on time to your lenders and creditors is one of the biggest contributing factors to your credit score, making up 35% of a FICO Score calculation. Your credit utilization, or the balance of your debt to available credit, contributes 30% to a FICO Score's calculation” (Fair Isaac Corporation).

Ensuring that you focus on making your payments on time and do not utilize your entire credit limit, then you should be able to increase and build your credit score. Moreover, I will discuss the adverse effects poor credit management has on students. College students may suffer from various personality traits that can adversely affect their credit. According to *Taylor & Francis Group*, “The four elemental personality traits are emotional instability, introversion, materialism, and the need for arousal- are found to be positively associated with credit card misuse”(Pirog III and Roberts 65). Having a credit card with thousands of dollars disposable at any instance can cause students to make irrational choices. Consequently, this leads to negative effects on the students that can affect both their financial and mental well-being. According to *Taylor & Francis*, “Students with higher consumer debt earn poorer grades, drop out of school, suffer from depression and work more hours to pay their bills”(Manning 200;Roberts and Jones 2001). This furthermore proves the point that students with higher credit debt suffer from negative cognitive and financial effects. As a result, many students are not fully aware of the responsibility and maturity that comes with credit leading to the misuse of it.

Assets & Liabilities

A key aspect of personal finance is knowing the difference between an asset and a liability to mitigate financial risks. Unfortunately, many individuals do not know the difference between the two and it may cause adverse effects to their finances. I surveyed fellow CSUF students and found that over 60% of students either never heard or were only sort of informed on assets and liabilities. Essentially, assets are things that you own and may appreciate over time, while liabilities are obligations or things you owe that can hinder one's progress. According to *accountingtools.com*, "The main difference between assets and liabilities is that assets provide a future economic benefit, while liabilities present a future obligation" (May 2022). Investing in assets will allow for a more well-balanced financial portfolio and less economic stress. On the

contrary, forgoing a lot of liabilities will cause financial stress and losses.

Nonetheless, not all liabilities are bad, and some are essential in order to get leverage and invest into your future. For example, taking out mortgage loans for real estate, school loans and even auto loans. The asset is the thing you own behind the liability so in this case it would be the car behind the auto loans, the house behind the mortgage loan and your education behind the student loans. These are all examples of liabilities that as students and adults we will need to take on, but do not necessarily mean that they are bad. According to *HanNa Lim (CFP) director*, “It is not always bad to have liabilities, especially if you are borrowing money for future you. This money can be leveraged and used to invest yourself. An example is going to college to get an education and have a higher chance at getting a well-paid job and a stable career” these liabilities are

essential to gain leverage and get a higher return on investment (ROI) over time. Furthermore, I will cover the two different types of student loans which are subsidized and unsubsidized student loans. It is crucial to understand the difference between these two loans in order to ensure you are paying the appropriate amount, interest, and time. Subsidized loans are federal loans disbursed by the United States Department of education to undergraduate students who qualify. The government pays the interest on the loan while you are in school and even offers a six-month grace period after graduation until you start paying interest. This can make a dramatic difference on paying less in student loans and saving by not paying the initial four years of interest. On the contrary, with unsubsidized loans you are required to pay interest as soon as the loans disburse which is as soon as you start university. This means that you are paying an extra four years of interest compared to subsidized loans. The main benefit of unsubsidized loans is that they are available to everyone and you can often receive a higher loan amount. Moreover, examples of more straightforward assets are precious metals, real estate, stocks, artwork, and businesses. Assets are anything that holds value, does not necessarily have to be monetary, and may continue to get better over time. Examples of liabilities are loans, credit card debt, taxes owed and even negative people. Liabilities can be anything that you owe, that is an obligation and hinders you from making progress. If you associate with negative people, it can adversely affect your life and hinder your progress. While it's completely impossible to 100% stay away from liabilities, it is important for college students to avoid any unnecessary liabilities as much as possible and instead invest in assets to ensure profitability and value in the future.

Certified Financial Planner (CFP) Director Interview: Lim, HanNa

1). What is the number one advice you would give to students in terms of personal finance?

The number one piece of advice I would give to students in terms of personal finance is to be more engaged in personal finance and to take care of household finances. There are different ways to engage and take care of household finances such as reviewing insurance policies, opening savings accounts, and checking accounts. This will allow students to learn early and get a head start on how to manage finances. My recommendation is for students to utilize financial resources that are available to help them invest. This can be learning on YouTube, taking a finance course at school or any online personal finance resources. It is important to start investing, even if it is in small amounts. Experience is important and helpful to learn; the earlier you start, the better you will be.

2). In Contrast, what do you think is the main point of personal finance that students lack?

The main point of personal finance that students lack is that they are not budgeting or tracking their expenses. In the finance classes that I teach, students have told me that they do not track expenses or have any budgets. Many of them are unaware of how many expenses they have such as subscriptions, shopping, dining out and other miscellaneous costs. Students must know where their money is going to ensure they are not overspending and can use the extra income to invest. Furthermore, students need to know the difference between fixed and variable expenses. Fixed expenses are amounts that you know are coming such as; rent, school tuition, utilities, gas. These are expenses that cannot be controlled and are just part of everyday life since they are necessities. On the other hand, Variable expenses are amounts that are fluctuating and expenses you can control. They are discretionary expenses such as; shopping, dining out, fast- food and travel. I recommend that students utilize spreadsheets and budgeting apps. My app recommendations are NerdWallet, ynab and goodbudget.

3). What is the recommended amount of money to have in an emergency fund?

The recommended amount of money to have in an emergency fund is about three to six months of living expenses. The main point of an emergency fund is to have money set aside for any unexpected adverse financial situations. Ensure to keep the money in highly liquid accounts such as; checking, savings, or short-term certificates of deposit just in case you need to withdraw the money. While certificates of deposit are less liquid than the other options, they most likely offer higher interest rates. My personal recommendation is to open a high-yield savings account to earn interest on your money and ensure that its FDIC backed up to \$250,000. That way the money is still liquid in case of an emergency and still earning interest.

4). What is the best way to build and increase credit as a student?

The number one thing for building credit is to never be late for your bill payments. This is the single most crucial factor affecting your credit score. Also, ensure that you never use the whole credit limit available. It is recommended to use less than 30% of the credit limit. This is also known as credit utilization. Furthermore, I recommend students to use student credit cards to build history, especially if you have no credit. This is a fantastic way for students to build and establish credit, without ever having credit history. The downside to student credit cards is that they typically offer lower credit limits and higher interest rates than traditional credit cards. Student credit cards are great, but as soon as you establish credit, switch to a traditional credit card to avoid higher rates and potentially higher credit limits.

5). Is it always bad to have liabilities?

It is not always bad to have liabilities, especially if you are borrowing money for future you. This money can be leveraged and used to invest yourself. An example is going to college to get an education and have a higher chance at getting a well-paid job and a stable career. Although you will most likely need to take out loans, they will provide a higher return in the long run. The

main liability that you want to avoid is credit card debt. Once you are in credit card debt it is extremely hard to climb your way out due to their very high interest rates. Nonetheless, anything that you use that provides value now or in the future such as; car, mortgage and student loans are not bad liabilities. It will provide value in the long term and may appreciate as time continues.

6). Do you recommend investing for students who are just starting to earn money?

I definitely recommend investing for students who are just starting to earn money, but one of the most important things is an individual's risk tolerance and time horizon. Risk tolerance is how comfortable you are with the possibility of losing money in your investments and time horizon refers to how much time you expect to hold an investment without needing the money back. If you are risk averse and not willing to take risks, then it is best to avoid the stock market and put money in high-yield savings accounts and certificates of deposit. That way your money can still be growing while at a certain interest rate and not be taking on any risk. On the contrary, if you have higher risk tolerance then you can start investing in the stock market. It is important to use diversification such as ETFs (exchange traded funds), Mutual Funds and Money Market Funds to mitigate your risk and possibly increase your return. A rule of thumb is to keep 80% in equity and the other 20% in fixed income/savings for young investors with a higher time horizon. For college students, they can take on more risk than people who are older due to a longer time horizon.

7). What is your opinion on High-yield savings accounts vs Money Market Funds?

Firstly, these are both great financial tools for students to start earning interest on their money with little to no risk. They provided similar interests usually at around 4.00% to 5.00%. There is more risk involved in a money market fund since they are not FDIC insured and its money invested into short-term fixed income assets such as short-term debt securities issued by governments and established corporations. Another difference is that there are minimum fees in

the Money market funds, while many high-yield savings accounts do not have fees. Money market funds are better for individuals who are willing to take on a little more risk and can possibly get a higher return from it.

Conclusion

In summary, it has become evident that students are not fully financially literate, and it has adversely affected their finances and physical & mental wellbeing. A variety of studies, posts on social media, and conversations with fellow college students have revealed that there's a lack of financial literacy within our community. Financial literacy matters because it directly correlates between financial stability and mental health, to avoid unnecessary debt, anxiety and depression. This project is dedicated to helping students become financially literate and boosting their lifelong success to mitigate the adverse effects poor financial choices may have on their mental health and finances. It includes a deep analysis of the four financial pillars: savings, investing, credit management, and assets & liabilities. These pillars represent the foundation of a successful, educated generation. The project includes valuable insight on the financial pillars from the director of the university's "Certified Financial Planner" program. A comprehensive survey of college students conducted to see if there is a lack of financial literacy within the student population. To inform this project, extensive research has been carried out on financial instruments and how students can utilize them to optimize their finances. Investing in financial literacy is investing in the future leaders and well-being of our generation, allowing us to make better life decisions. "Education is the key to unlocking the world, a passport to freedom" (Oprah Winfrey).

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